

Dental nurse support for all dental hygienists and therapists

by **MARJAN ELYASSI**

As we are all too aware, severe periodontal diseases are estimated to affect around 14% of the global adult population, representing more than one billion cases worldwide.¹ Periodontitis is currently the 6th most prevalent disease globally.² Dental hygienists are trained to screen, and treat periodontal diseases: their contribution to the provision of oral healthcare and prevention of disease is considerable.

However, there are reports that dental care professionals, especially dental hygienists, are at high risk of burnout, emotional exhaustion and fear of litigation. This is associated with everyday stressors: long working hours; musculoskeletal pain; difficult or demanding patients; time constraints; and working without assistance.^{3,4,5} Dental hygienists, unlike their dentist colleagues, often work without dental nurse support.

Background

The British Society of Dental Hygiene and Therapy (BSDHT) continues to lobby for chairside dental nurse support for its members. A body of evidence is being compiled to support their argument.^{5,6}

Harris and Eaton (2021)⁶ found that of 1782 respondent dental hygienist members of BSDHT, 749 (43%) had dental nurse support all of the time; 578 (33%) some of the time but 420 (24%) never had dental nurse support. Furthermore, 1176 (67%) respondents were 'extremely concerned' about working without dental nurse support. Their results showed that over time, stress and burnout can negatively impact performance and wellbeing of dental hygienists.

McClune and Reed (2021)⁵ investigated the experience of dental hygienists working with chairside dental nurse assistance in general dental practices in Southern England. The researchers aimed to establish whether routine chairside dental nurse assistance enables or inhibits clinical working conditions for dental hygienists. Unsurprisingly, most of the dental hygienist respondents reported positive benefits from having full time dental nurse support. All participants reported increased job satisfaction, a reduction in occupational stress and improved patient treatment outcomes when supported at the chairside by a dental nurse colleague.

Additional pressures during the COVID-19 pandemic had a severe impact on clinicians.⁷ Dramatic changes to cross infection and decontamination procedures - such as mandatory wearing of FFP2/3 masks, prohibition of aerosol-generating procedures (AGPs), time allocation in between the patients - had an impact on our mental health. In many, cases dental practices had no choice but to provide dental hygienists with dental nurse support.

Currently

There are more than 8261 dental hygienists and therapists on the GDC register with an increased entry rate annually of 11%.⁹

In the General Dental Council guidance: GDC Standards for the Dental Team, section 6.2 states: You must be appropriately supported when treating patients. Section 6.2.1. states: You must not provide treatment if you feel that the circumstances make it unsafe for patients. 6.2.2. states: You should work with another appropriately trained member of the dental team at all times when treating patients in a dental setting.⁸

However, while the presence of dental nurse support is compulsory for dentists - the GDC includes the word 'must' - it is not the same for dental hygienists and therapists - the GDC word of choice is 'should'. The GDC also states: '...the duty would not apply in all situations, and where there are exceptional circumstances outside your control that could affect whether, or how, you can comply with the guidance.' 'Should' is also used when we are '...providing an explanation of how you will meet the overriding duty based on GDC Standards'.⁸

Encouragingly, the British Association of Dental Nurses (BADN), has offered BSDHT its support. Meanwhile BUPA, as a private healthcare company, has already started recruiting chairside dental nurses for all dental hygienists in all its dental practices.

Making full-time dental nurse support mandatory will not only reduce the pressure on dental hygienists but also benefit the patients. It is worrying however that Eaton and Harris (2021)⁶ found that 366 (22%) of dental hygienist respondents had been advised by their principal dentist that a reduction in their salary would be necessary if they wanted full-time dental nurse support!

Multitaskers

Stress produces both adaptive and maladaptive effects on the brain.¹⁰ One of the main elements that increases stress hormones is working conditions.¹¹ Dental hygienists need to employ theoretical and critical thinking skills, in parallel with clinical skills, to carry out clinical operative procedures, alongside working with members of the dental team. Struggling to single handedly record indices, undertake excellent decontamination procedures and provide tailored patient care, within the time constraints of an appointment, impacts emotionally and physically. It is also necessary to be aware of any potential litigation risks, particularly in the absence of a dental nurse, who also acts as a witness and chaperone.

The role of a dental hygienist is fundamental to the successful

prevention of dental diseases, in any practice. Full-time dental nurse support will help us all become better clinicians and hopefully increase our job satisfaction and our professional longevity in a vocation about which we are all so passionate.

Recommendations

The GDC needs to review their wording in the Standards guidance. In the meantime, the support of dental indemnity providers is needed. As ever, we need to continue to build a body of evidence that proves what every clinician is only too aware: helping to improve the oral health of the nation requires a team effort.

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